

Supplemental Table S1 and S2

Supplemental Table S1. Clinical data of hepatocellular carcinoma patients

Case No. in current study	Sex	Age (years)	Indication for liver surgery	Location of biopsy	Used in research
1	Male	66	HCC	Right lobe	Tissue clearing (TC)
2	Female	61	Hepatocellular-cholangiocarcinoma	Left lobe	Not used
3	Male	51	HCC	Right lobe	TC
4	Male	67	HCC & end-stage renal disease	Right lobe	Not used
5	Male	39	HCC	Left lobe	TC
6	Male	55	Cirrhosis & HCC	Left lobe	Not used (cirrhosis)
7	Male	75	HCC	Right lobe	Not used (age)
8	Male	71	HCC	Right lobe	Not used (age)
9	Female	45	HCC	Right lobe	IF & TC
10	Female	78	HCC	Right lobe	Not used (age)
11	Male	69	HCC	Right lobe	IF & TC
12	Female	62	Cirrhosis & HCC	Right lobe	Not used (cirrhosis)
13	Female	55	Cirrhosis & HCC	Left lobe	Not used (cirrhosis)
14	Female	52	HCC	Right lobe	IF & TC
15	Male	61	HCC	Right lobe	IF & TC
16	Male	71	HCC	Left lobe	Not used (age)
17	Female	74	HCC	Right lobe	Not used (age)
18	Male	64	HCC	Left lobe	IF & TC
19	Female	55	HCC	Right lobe	IF & TC

HCC: hepatocellular carcinoma; TC: tissue clearing; IF: immunofluorescence labeling

Supplemental Table S2. Pancreas organ donor information

Case No. in current study	Sex	Age (years)	BMI	HbA _{1c} % (mmol/mol)	Cause of death	Used in research
1	Female	51	19.8	5.3% (34)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	IF & TC
2	Female	51	22.8	5.4% (36)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	IF & TC
3	Male	40	20.4	5.5% (37)	Asphyxiation	IF & TC

TC: tissue clearing; IF: immunofluorescence labeling

Supplemental Table S3

Supplemental Table S3. Summary of primary antibodies used in illustrations.

		Primary antibody (category number)	Dilution	Color code
Figure 2	panel B-D	tyrosine hydroxylase (AB152)	1: 100	Green
		CD31 (ab215912)	1: 100	Red
	panel I-T	CD31 (ab215912)	1: 100	Red
Figure 3	panel B-V	substance P (MAB356)	1: 100	Cyan
		PGP9.5 (ab108986)	1: 100	Magenta
Figure 4	panel B-U	tyrosine hydroxylase (AB152)	1: 100	Green
		PGP9.5 (ab196173)	1: 100	Magenta
Figure 5	panel A-I	tyrosine hydroxylase (AB152)	1: 100	Green
Figure 6	panel A-C	vesicular acetylcholine transporter (139103)	1: 100	Yellow
		CK19 (ab7755)	1: 100	Cyan
	panel D-O	vesicular acetylcholine transporter (139103)	1: 100	Yellow
		PGP9.5 (ab196173)	1: 100	Magenta
Suppl. Fig. S3	panel A-D	tyrosine hydroxylase (AB152)	1: 100	Green
Suppl. Fig. S4	panel A-G	vesicular acetylcholine transporter (139103)	1: 100	Yellow
		PGP9.5 (ab196173)	1: 100	Magenta
	panel H-Q	vesicular acetylcholine transporter (139103)	1: 100	Yellow
		PGP9.5 (ab196173)	1: 100	Magenta
	panel R-Z	vesicular acetylcholine transporter (139103)	1: 100	Yellow
		PGP9.5 (ab196173)	1: 100	Magenta

Note: tyrosine hydroxylase (TH, sympathetic marker); CD31 (endothelial marker); substance P (SP, sensory nerve marker); PGP9.5 (pan-neuronal/neuroendocrine marker); vesicular acetylcholine transporter (VAChT, parasympathetic marker); CK19 (epithelial marker).

Supplemental Table S4

Supplemental Table S4. Summary of color codes presented in illustrations.

		Magenta/Red	Green	Yellow	Blue/cyan	White	Gray
Figure 2	panel A, E (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel B-D (fluorescence image)	CD31	TH			nuclei	transmitted light
	panel F (Masson's trichrome stain), G, H (H&E image)						
	panel I-L (fluorescence image)	CD31				nuclei	
	panel M-T (fluorescence image)	CD31				nuclei	transmitted light
Figure 3	panel A, J (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel B-I, K-V (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5			substance P	nuclei	transmitted light
Figure 4	panel A, G (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel B-F, H-U (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5	TH			nuclei	transmitted light
Figure 5	panel A-E, G-I (fluorescence image)		TH			nuclei	
Figure 6	panel A-O (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5		VACHT	CK19	nuclei	
Suppl. Fig. S3	panel A-D (fluorescence image)		TH			nuclei	
Suppl. Fig. S4	panel A (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel B-G (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5		VACHT		nuclei	
	panel H (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel I-Q (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5		VACHT		nuclei	
	panel R (stereomicroscopic image)						
	panel S-Z (fluorescence image)	PGP9.5		VACHT		nuclei	

Note: CD31 (endothelial marker); tyrosine hydroxylase (TH, sympathetic marker); substance P (SP, sensory nerve marker); PGP9.5 (pan-neuronal/neuroendocrine marker); vesicular acetylcholine transporter (VACHT, parasympathetic marker); CK19 (epithelial marker).